

INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE TEACHER: ESSENCE AND STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS

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Abstract. *The article deals with the development of information competencies in future teachers. The substantiation of the relevance of this problem, a description of the principles and goals that should underlie the process of developing information competencies in future teachers is presented. A computer is just a tool, the use of which should organically fit into the system of education and upbringing, contribute to the achievement of the goals and objectives of the lesson or extracurricular activities. The computer does not replace the teacher or the textbook, but radically changes the nature of pedagogical activity. The main methodological problem of teaching is shifting from “how best to tell the material” to “how best to show”. Assimilation of knowledge related to a large amount of digital and other specific information through active dialogue with a personal computer is more effective and interesting for the student than studying the boring pages of a textbook. With the help of training programs, a student can simulate real processes, which means he can see causes and effects, understand their meaning. The computer allows you to eliminate one of the most important reasons for a negative attitude to learning - failure due to a lack of understanding of the essence of the problem, significant gaps in knowledge.*

Key words: *information competencies, educators, learning, learning technologies, culture and ethics of working with information, critical thinking, professional development.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрены вопросы развития информационных компетентностей у будущих педагогов. Представлено обоснование актуальности данной проблемы, описание принципов и целей, которые должны лежать в основе процесса развития информационных компетентностей у будущих педагогов. Компьютер – всего лишь инструмент, использование которого должно органично вписываться в систему обучения и воспитания, способствовать достижению поставленных целей и задач урока или внеклассного мероприятия. Компьютер не заменяет учителя или учебник, но коренным образом меняет характер педагогической деятельности. Главная методическая проблема преподавания смещается от того, «как лучше рассказать материал», к тому, «как лучше показать». Усвоение знаний, связанных с большим объёмом цифровой и иной конкретной информации, путём активного диалога с персональным компьютером более эффективно и интересно для ученика, чем штудирование скучных страниц учебника. С помощью обучающих программ ученик может моделировать реальные процессы, а значит – видеть причины и следствия, понимать их смысл. Компьютер позволяет устранить одну из важнейших причин отрицательного отношения к учёбе – неуспех, обусловленный непониманием сути проблемы, значительными пробелами в знаниях.*

Ключевые слова: *информационные компетентности, воспитателей, обучения, технологии обучения, культура и этика работы с информацией, критическое мышление, профессиональное развитие.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarda axborot kompetentsiyalarini rivojlantirish haqida so‘z boradi. Ushbu muammoning dolzarbligini asoslash, bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarda axborot kompetentsiyalarini rivojlantirish jarayoniga asos bo‘lishi kerak*

bo'lgan tamoyillar va maqsadlarning tavsifi keltirilgan. Kompyuter shunchaki vosita bo'lib, undan foydalanish ta'lim va tarbiya tizimiga organik ravishda mos kelishi, darsning yoki darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarning maqsad va vazifalariga erishishga hissa qo'shishi kerak. Kompyuter o'qituvchi yoki darslikni almastirmaydi, balki pedagogik faoliyatning mohiyatini tubdan o'zgartiradi. O'qitishning asosiy uslubiy muammosi "materialni qanday qilib yaxshiroq aytib berish" dan "qanday qilib eng yaxshi ko'rsatish" ga o'tishdir. Darslikning zerikarli sahifalarini o'rganishdan ko'ra, katta hajmdagi raqamli va boshqa aniq ma'lumotlarga oid bilimlarni shaxsiy kompyuter bilan faol muloqot orqali o'zlashtirish talaba uchun samaraliroq va qiziqarliroqdir. O'quv dasturlari yordamida talaba real jarayonlarni taqlid qilishi mumkin, ya'ni u sabab va oqibatlarni ko'ra oladi, ularning ma'nosini tushunadi. Kompyuter o'rganishga salbiy munosabatning eng muhim sabablaridan birini - muammoning mohiyatini tushunmaslik tufayli muvaffaqiyatsizlikni, bilimdagi sezilarli bo'shliqlarni yo'q qilishga imkon beradi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** axborot kompetentsiyalari, pedagoglar, ta'lim, ta'lim texnologiyalari, axborot bilan ishlash madaniyati va etikasi, tanqidiy fikrlash, kasbiy rivojlanish.*

The modern period of life in Uzbekistan is characterized by the fact that the education system is being brought into line with the needs of society, which is moving to a new stage of its development - information. The discovery of the didactic capabilities of information and communication technologies (ICT) and their implementation in the educational process, the development of the Internet and the provision of new network services actualize the continuous improvement of the teacher's information competence.

The introduction of ICT into the professional activities of teachers is inevitable in our time. Teacher professionalism is a synthesis of competencies, including subject-methodological, psychological-pedagogical and ICT components.

Acquiring information competence opens up a wide range of opportunities for teachers and students that enrich the educational environment and make the learning and education process more dynamic.

Currently, not only the teaching community, but also society as a whole understands that computer proficiency (computer literacy) is an essential element of education. One of the results of the informatization process should be the emergence in teachers of the ability to use modern information and communication technologies to work with information. They must be able to search for the necessary data, process, analyze and evaluate it, as well as produce and disseminate information in accordance with their purposes. The formation of information competence is the process of transition to a state where the teacher becomes able to find, understand, evaluate and apply information in various forms to solve personal, social or global problems. Information competence of a teacher is the ability of a teacher to use digital technologies, means of communication and/or computer networks to access, manage, integrate, evaluate and create educational information for the purpose of effective professional functioning in the existing information and educational environment, in other words, under the information competence of a teacher one should understand not only the use of various information tools, but also their effective application in teaching activities. (Annex 1)

To develop ICT competence it is necessary:

- the presence of ideas about the functioning of a PC and the didactic capabilities of ICT;
- mastering the methodological foundations of preparing visual and didactic materials using Microsoft Office;
- use of the Internet and digital educational resources in teaching activities;

- formation of positive motivation to use ICT.

A computer is just a tool, the use of which should organically fit into the system of education and upbringing, contribute to the achievement of the goals and objectives of a lesson or extracurricular activity. The computer does not replace the teacher or the textbook, but radically changes the nature of pedagogical activity. The main methodological problem of teaching shifts from “how best to tell the material” to “how best to show it.”

Mastering knowledge related to a large volume of digital and other specific information through active dialogue with a personal computer is more effective and interesting for the student than studying boring pages of a textbook. With the help of training programs, a student can simulate real processes, which means he can see causes and consequences and understand their meaning. The computer allows you to eliminate one of the most important reasons for a negative attitude towards learning - failure due to a lack of understanding of the essence of the problem, significant gaps in knowledge.

The inclusion of ICT in the course of a lesson, activity, or event makes the process of learning and education interesting and entertaining, creates a cheerful, working mood in children, and makes it easier to overcome difficulties in mastering the material. Various aspects of the use of information and computer technologies support and enhance children’s interest in the academic subject. The computer can and should be considered as a powerful lever for the mental development of a child.

The use of new information technologies in teaching and upbringing makes it possible to develop special skills in children with different cognitive abilities and makes the educational process more visual and dynamic.

Computer technology capabilities:

1. Computer as a means of searching for information:
 - Internet resources;
 - Electronic reference books and encyclopedias;
 - Databases;
 - Music libraries;
 - Video libraries;
2. Computer as a means of information processing:
 - Creation of a database for students;
 - Performance analysis;
 - Attendance recording;
 - Accounting for individual achievements of students;
 - Processing of questionnaires;
3. Computer as a means of storing information:
 - Databases, photo and video archives, electronic museums;
 - Photo albums in electronic form;
 - Collections of creative works of students and teachers in electronic form;
 - Video archive;
 - Website;
4. Computer as a means of providing visibility:
 - Presentations and other demonstration forms;
 - Websites;
 - Publishing activities;

- school newspapers;
 - Express materials for stands using a digital camera, etc.;
 - Situation modeling;

5. Computer as a means of communication:

- Website, mail, etc.;
- Guest book;
- Email;
- Teleconferences and teleconferences;
- Forums, etc.

Thus, a high level of information competence is an important characteristic of a modern teacher, allowing one to reach a new level of pedagogical skill and ensuring high-quality training of future specialists. (ANNEX 1)

The use of information technology in the educational process makes this process more modern, diverse, rich, significantly expands the possibilities of presenting educational information, has a complex effect on different channels of perception, on various types of memory, ensures the handling of large volumes of information, clarity, beauty, and aesthetics of the design of educational activities, makes the upbringing process more attractive for children, increases interest in activities, promotes the child's adaptation in the modern information space and the formation of an information culture.

ICTs are used in various forms of educational activities and are combined with various information sources and pedagogical technologies, they allow a more qualitative system of diagnostics and monitoring of the educational process, improve the quality of pedagogical work, and contribute to the effectiveness of educational activities. Competent, systematic use of information and communication technologies can and should become a powerful modern means of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process.

Modern computer equipment in the educational process is:

- as a means for creating information and methodological materials and documents (plans, notes, methodological developments, etc.);
- as a means of providing visibility (presentations, videos, videos and other demonstration forms);
- as a means of searching for information (text, video and audio);
- as a means of processing information (photo and video images, text information, processing questionnaires, constructing diagrams, graphs when studying the dynamics of certain processes in educational activities);
- as a means of storing information (databases, methodological developments and collections, photo and video archives, electronic repositories);

• as a means of communication (website, e-mail, forums, chats, etc.).

Structure of ICT – Teacher Competence

The range of use of ICT in the educational process is quite wide. Teachers of the state institution of preschool education in the educational and pedagogical complex in kindergarten No. 74 "Book" - "junior group" use information technologies as follows:

1. As a means of visual design and information support of educational events (presentation illustrative materials for class hours and school events, questionnaires, testing, video support of concerts, evenings, holidays, etc.).

2. Organization of the activities of a modern press center, where computer equipment acts as a means of developing the creative abilities of students and preparing them for primary education.

3. Creation and organization of activities of computer classrooms of interest, where teachers acquire skills in working with computer equipment, master programming technologies, carry out creative projects for the development of new electronic resources, and are engaged in research activities.

4. Creation of Internet communities and network associations, the program of which includes debates and discussions of Internet materials, trainings, business games, participation in network conferences, forums, chats in order to meet intellectual and creative needs, the formation of information culture, value orientations of teachers. For the youngest children, cartoons and games are offered, through which elementary school students form the basics of economic culture and financial literacy.

5. Creation of classroom multimedia libraries (media tech) to accompany and organize various educational events (presentations, reviews, round tables, discussions, meetings, etc.)

6. Creation and organization of multimedia laboratories, the main purpose of which is the production of multimedia products for the needs of the classroom and kindergarten. Teachers of the educational institution have created and operate electronic means of teaching for the computer.

7. Organization of research activities using ICT.

8. Participation of teachers in online Olympiads in various areas and areas of knowledge created with the help of the MOODLE service or Google Forms.

9. Creation of websites, web-pages, blogs of children's associations, creative teams and the use of their capabilities in the system of educational activities.

The multifunctionality of information technologies ensures their effective use in the management system of the educational process.

Variability of the use of ICT in the management of the educational process:

1. Creation of a collection of electronic resources to help teachers of additional education.
2. Use of ready-made resources: software products for organizing a management system for electronic magazines, newspapers, websites, reference books, multimedia libraries, etc.
3. Organization of electronic document management in accordance with the requirements for educational documentation (planning, packages of administrative documentation, electronic archives, databases).
4. Organization of a unified informational, educational environment of EI (local network, EI website, database of electronic educational resources, unified database of regulatory, analytical and current documentation, information exchange, etc.).
5. Automation of the processes of monitoring educational activities: computer testing, processing of diagnostic results using a computer; creation of databases based on the results of monitoring.
6. Use of network technologies (Internet conferences, forums, blogs) in the system of methodological activities of educators, teachers of additional education, in the organization of the activities of children's groups.

The use of information and communication technologies in the educational process is not limited to the use of a computer as a typewriter for the preparation of any illustrative materials. And it's not limited to just showcasing presentations. It is the use of the full potential of digital educational resources to achieve the set goals.

Experience shows that the creation of a single information space for education through the use of ICT in educational work contributes to increasing the interest of students in everything that happens in kindergarten, stimulates the cognitive and creative activity of children. All of the above confirms the growth of the quality of educational work in schools, the increase in the level of its organization, and makes the educational process modern in terms of form and content.

The effectiveness of the use of information technologies largely depends on a clear understanding of the place that they should occupy in the complex complex of interconnections that arise in the system of interaction between the educator and the child.

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